

USE OF THIOSEMICARBAZONES AS REAGENTS IN INORGANIC ANALYSIS

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Thiosemicarbazones of six aldehydes and ketones have been tested as reagents for the common inorganic cations at different pH ranges and the resulting colour changes, formation of precipitates as well as the solubilities of the precipitated complexes noted. Precipitates are formed with Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} and Cu^{2+} in all cases and in some cases with Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} , but with Ba^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in one case only. The thiosemicarbazones of *p*-hydroxybenzophenone, piperonal and benzoin have been found good for the quantitative estimation of Cu^{2+} and those of piperonal and veratraldehyde, to furnish quantitative precipitates with Hg^{2+} . Veratral and *m*-hydroxybenzylidene derivatives have been found to be highly sensitive for Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} even at 1:10 dilutions. Some of the thiosemicarbazones also exhibited colorations with some anions as ferricyanide, ferrocyanide, nitrite, molybdate, chromate, thiocyanate, borate, tungstate and thiosulphate.

Neuberg and Neiman (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2049) first found that the thiosemicarbazones of a few aldehydes and ketones could be used for identifying Ag, Hg and Cu as they afforded sparingly soluble derivatives with these metals in solution due to formation of complexes. This investigation was therefore taken up in order to determine the range of such complex formation under properly controlled conditions and also their solubilities and stabilities as well as their use in quantitative estimations of metals.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The thiosemicarbazones of six aldehydes and ketones were prepared by the methods of Neuberg and Neiman (*loc. cit.*) and Scott *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1767). All the compounds are new except *p*-aminoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone which has been prepared according to the method of Guha Sircar and Satpathy (*this Journal*, 1954, 31, 550), Mitra and Guha Sircar (*ibid.*, 1955, 32, 433) and Indian Patent (1950, 43527).

The melting points and the analytical data of the thiosemicarbazones are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

	Aldehydes or ketones.	M.P.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzophenone	186°	11.71	11.82
2.	Piperonal	185°	15.38	15.46
3.	Veratraldehyde	200°	14.26	14.35
4.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	173°	16.36	16.41
5.	<i>p</i> -Aminoacetophenone	178°	15.52	15.39
6.	Benzoin	174°	11.13	11.29

An 1% solution of the reagent in rectified spirit was added dropwise to 10 drops of each of 2N solutions of salts of metals arranged in their analytical order (Ag, Hg, Pb, Cu, Cd, Bi, As, Sb, Sn, Fe, Al, Cr, Co, Ni, Zn, Mn, Ca, Sr, Ba, Mg) in a series of test tubes containing 2 c.c. of an acetate buffer solution of p_{H} between 3.42 and 5.89. The formation of any precipitate or colour change in the mixture was noted both in cold and on heating. When the precipitate was formed, its precipitation was completed by further addition of the reagent and warming the mixture on the water-bath. The precipitate was filtered, washed and the filtrate tested for the respective cation by further addition of the reagent solution. The p_{H} ranges suitable for coagulation of precipitates were noted and the precipitation was taken to be quantitative. The complexes were further washed with alcohol to free them of the reagent and their solubilities in dilute HCl, ammonia, acetone, alcohol and chloroform were qualitatively studied. The complexes were also decomposed by strong mineral acids and the liberated cations were tested by some standard reagents for ascertaining the actual formation of the complex.

Reactions of the Reagents with the Cations at Different p_{H} (3.42-5.89)

p-Hydroxybenzophenone thiosemicarbazone formed yellow precipitate with Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , the silver complex first turning brown and finally black in light. Ni^{2+} gave a white precipitate, changing to buff and Co^{3+} gave a deep red colour on standing. Cu^{2+} formed a green precipitate, turning black on heating and was quantitative, soluble in mineral acids but insoluble in ammonia, acetone, chloroform, alcohol and water.

Piperonal thiosemicarbazone gave a yellow precipitate with Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , white with Ba^{3+} and Mg^{2+} and a green precipitate with Cu^{2+} . The Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} precipitates were quantitative, soluble in mineral acids but insoluble in ammonia, acetone, chloroform and alcohol.

Veratraldehyde thiosemicarbazone gave a yellow gel with Ag^+ and Hg^{2+} , turning black and green respectively on heating. Cu^{2+} formed a green precipitate. Hg^{2+} complex was quantitative and soluble in strong mineral acids, insoluble in dilute acids, dilute ammonia and alcohol.

m-Hydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone formed a white precipitate with Ag^+ and Hg^{2+} , green with Cu^{2+} and chocolate with Co^{3+} . Ni^{2+} gave a red colour on standing. The Ag^+ precipitate was quantitative, soluble in dilute HNO_3 but sparingly soluble in alcohol and water.

p-Aminoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone gave a yellow precipitate with Ag^+ and Hg^{2+} , the silver complex turning black in light. The precipitates were not quantitative.

Benzoin thiosemicarbazone gave a yellow precipitate with Ag^+ and Hg^{2+} , the silver complex turning black in light. The precipitate with Cu^{2+} was bluish green, quantitative, soluble in mineral acids but insoluble in ammonia, alcohol, acetone, chloroform and water.

The reactions of the anions in neutral as well as in acid media were studied. The anions tested were ferricyanide, ferrocyanide, nitrite, molybdate, chromate, tungstate,

thiocyanate, thiosulphate and borate. To about 3 c.c. of the anion solution 5 drops of an 1% solution of the reagent in rectified spirit were slowly added and the colour changes were noted both in the cold and on warming. In case of ferricyanide, ferrocyanide, chromate and nitrite, two sets of solutions were used. To one set 5 drops of glacial acetic acid and 5 drops of the reagent solution were added and to the other set only 5 drops of acetic acid were added. The changes in coloration, whether immediate or delayed, were observed.

Colour Changes with the Reagents in Neutral and Acidic Media with Anions

p-Hydroxybenzophenone thiosemicarbazone produced colour changes in acidic medium with ferricyanide, ferrocyanide, nitrite, molybdate chromate and thiocyanate, the colour being respectively green, yellow, blue, bluish green and red. In neutral medium it gave a yellow colour with chromate.

Piperonal thiosemicarbazone produced a bluish green coloration with ferrocyanide, molybdate and chromate and a red colour with thiocyanate in acid medium. In neutral medium it gave a yellow precipitate with ferrocyanide.

Veratraldehyde thiosemicarbazone gave a green coloration with ferricyanide and chromate, a yellow colour with nitrite and a light blue colour with molybdate in acid medium. In neutral medium, it gave a yellow precipitate with ferrocyanide.

m-Hydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone produced a blue colour with ferricyanide, green coloration with ferrocyanide, molybdate and chromate and yellow with nitrite and thiosulphate in acid medium. In neutral medium it gave a yellow precipitate with ferrocyanide.

p-Aminoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone gave a green colour with ferrocyanide and tungstate, yellow with nitrite and blue with molybdate in acid medium.

Benzoin thiosemicarbazone produced green, yellow, blue and blood-red colorations with ferrocyanide, nitrite, molybdate and chromate respectively in acid medium. In neutral medium, it gave a yellow precipitate with ferrocyanide and molybdate.

In the case of coloured complexes different dilutions of the cation solutions were prepared and the sensitivity of the reagents for them was noted both in solution and by spot test on a filter paper. The sensitivity of the reagents towards metallic cations is mentioned in Table II.

TABLE II
(1 g. in c.c.)

Cation.	Serial number of reagents					
	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
Ag ⁺	10 ⁵	10 ⁶	10 ⁷	10 ⁴	10 ⁵	10 ⁵
Hg ²⁺	10 ⁵	10 ⁴	10 ⁴	10 ³	10 ⁵	10 ⁴
Cu ²⁺	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁴	10 ⁵	10 ⁴	10 ⁴
Co ²⁺	10 ⁶	...	...	10 ⁶	...	...
Ni ²⁺	10 ⁴	10 ⁶	...	10 ⁷	...	...

Spot Test.—In case of Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} , a drop of the cationic solution was placed on the filter paper, dried and treated with a drop of an 1% alcoholic solution of the reagent. The spot was then exposed to ammonia vapour.

Quantitative Estimations

Quantitative estimations could not be made with Ag, Ni and Co complexes as they were very unstable and liable to decomposition on drying. Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} were estimated quantitatively.

Estimation of Cu^{2+} .—The standard solution (10 c.c.) was taken in a beaker and after addition of an acetate buffer (100 c.c.) of p_H 4.99 was heated to 50° - 60° . A hot 1 or 2% solution of the reagent in rectified spirit was added dropwise with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The temperature was maintained at 50° - 60° for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with occasional stirring. It was allowed to settle for 1 hour and filtered when cold. The precipitate was first washed with hot water and then with 2% alcohol and dried at $100-105^{\circ}$ to a constant weight. The results assuming 1:1 combination between *p*-hydroxybenzophenone thiosemicarbazone and Cu and 2:1 between piperonal or benzoin thiosemicarbazones and Cu are recorded below.

TABLE III

Standard soln. taken = 10 c.c.

Wt. of the complex.	Reagent No.		
	1.	2.	6.
Mean (g.)	0.1654	0.2564	0.3120
Calc. (g.)	0.1663	0.2588	0.3158

The structures of the complexes of reagents No. 1 (I) and 2 or 3 (II) may be represented as:

(R = ketonic ligand for reagent No. 1)

(R = aldehydic or ketonic ligand for reagents No. 2 & 3)

A weighed amount of the copper complex was taken in a weighed porcelain crucible and decomposed by HNO_3 (1:1). The acid was evaporated to dryness and the complex ignited to a constant weight. The difference in weight of CuO from the calculated percentage of copper is recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

	Reagent No.		
	1.	2.	6.
% Cu (found)	19.31	11.88	9.94
% Cu (calc.)	19.11	12.27	10.07

Estimation of Hg²⁺ Complex.—To a standard solution (10 c.c.) of mercury in a beaker an acetate buffer (50 c.c.) at p_H 5.6 was added, followed by 2% alcoholic solution of the reagent dropwise with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The mixture was allowed to settle for 3 to 4 hours, filtered and washed first with slightly warm water and then with 2% alcohol. The rest of the procedure was the same as with Cu complex. With reagent No. 2 mean wt. of the complex found was 0.2128 g. (calc. 0.2108 g.). Mean wt. of the complex with reagent No. 3 found was 0.2204 g. (calc. 0.2188 g.).

The weights of the complexes were slightly high due to the difficulty in removing the reagents by washing. The structure of these complexes corresponds to the structure as mentioned above.

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